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CLASSIFICATION OF TECHNOLOGIES BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND AI

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Abstract: This article provides information on the concepts of artificial intelligence, known as AI, which is considered as one of the current topics, as well as their main tasks, their importance in human life, and the analysis of the functions performed based on them. At the same time, the most The technology used, namely ChatGPT, is explained in more detail.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Data Analytics, NLP, ChatGPT, Machine Translation, DeepL and Microsoft Translator

КЛАССИФИКАЦИЯ ИИ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА ОСНОВЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА

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Аннотация: В данной статье представлена информация о концепции искусственного интеллекта, известного как ИИ, которая рассматривается как одна из актуальных тем, а также об их основных задачах, их значении в жизни человека и анализе выполняемых на их основе функций. При этом более подробно объясняется наиболее используемая технология, а именно ChatGPT.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, анализ данных, NLP, ChatGPT, машинный перевод, DeepL и Microsoft Translator.

The main part. Artificial intelligence (from the English language “Artificial intelligence”) is currently the most popular, widely used by people, and has been applied to many fields. Artificial intelligence (SI) or (AI) is a name that summarizes all technological processes and programs that provide the ability to learn, manage and perform other tasks through technological systems. The main purpose of artificial intelligence is to automate, provide and perform well human thoughts and actions. These technologies are widely used in every field. It is a technological concept used to study, analyze and implement mental information generated by computers and other smart devices or programs to solve human-like problems. Artificial intelligence systems are programmed to process information, learn, find logical solutions, analyze data, and perform highly complex tasks.

Artificial intelligence is a technology that studies computer programs, mainly data analysis, analysis and general labeling. It works by collecting a lot of data, statistics, information and documents with its own systems and algorithms, identifying things from them and showing results. Artificial intelligence is used in business, medicine, education and many other fields. In short, artificial intelligence is a system or technology capable of imitating human behavior in performing certain tasks, and the obtained ma It gradually improves using data. In general, artificial intelligence is neither a format nor a function, but a process that includes data collection, analysis, etc. When talking about artificial intelligence, it is necessary to analyze its place in business and information technology. The gradual penetration of artificial intelligence into these areas will ensure an increase in the number of artificial intelligence tools. By "artificial intelligence" most people understand the involvement of robots in various fields. But the term artificial intelligence does not mean that robots will replace humans. Its main goal is to expand the limits of human abilities and capabilities. That's why technologies like this are a valuable business resource. At first, the term "artificial intelligence" was applied to tasks that could only be performed by humans, such as customer service or playing chess. Also, the deep learning of computer technology is considered as artificial intelligence. But customer service, various online games and deep learning of computer technologies are considered a small part of artificial intelligence technologies. It's true that artificial intelligence technologies help improve productivity by automating tasks that humans perform. However, now its scope is expanding, now with artificial intelligence it is possible to determine the character of people, the abilities of students, the views of the employee towards work. Many technologies have been created based on it, for example: Data Analytics, Artificial Speech (Natural Language Processing - NLP), Artificial Skills (Machine Learning - ML),

Artificial Skills indicators (Artificial Neural Networks), Robotics, Artificial Reality (Artificial Reality), Trap Artificial Intelligence (Distributed Artificial Intelligence, Learning (Machine Learning), Digital Image (Computer Vision), Natural Science (Natural Language Processing), Guide (Applications), Security and Privacy, Google assistance, chat gpt, Google translator, etc.

Data Analytics: This technology is based on data analysis, statistics, and data control. It is part of artificial intelligence and is used in distance education, cryptography, marketing and other fields. Data exploration and discovery with the support of artificial intelligence algorithms.

Natural Language Processing (NLP): This technology deals with human language, speaking and writing. Search engines, speech engines, translators, and other artificial intelligence technologies use NLP.

Machine Learning (ML): Machine Learning uses algorithms to learn, understand, and discover based on empirical data and data. This technology allows learning and performing intellectual tasks without having to write code for writing.

Artificial Neural Networks: This technology is a part of artificial intelligence that works on the principle of human learning from other people. These networks work in data exploration, classification and other intellectual tasks.

Robotics: Robots and robotics technologies are also a type of artificial intelligence. This includes technologies related to the creation, development, and use of robots and other automated systems. Robotics: Performing tasks using robots through artificial intelligence systems.

Reality: This technology includes virtual reality (VR) and cyber reality (AR). These turias take a person to another realm of death and destroy him.

Intelligence: This technology includes emerging forms of artificial intelligence in the application, construction, and operation of powerful connected systems for future control.

Learning (Machine Learning): Supervised learning: Predicting new information based on information learned from a teacher. Unsupervised learning (Unsupervised learning): Between data determining boundaries without the need for direct detection. Reinforcement learning: Learning through rewards and punishments to return correct results to the system.

Digital Vision (Computer Vision): Object recognition: Preparing artificial intelligence systems for object recognition and understanding. Working with colors: Preparing artificial intelligence systems for color recognition and understanding.

Natural Language Processing: Language learning: Training artificial intelligence systems to learn and understand human language. Translation: Translating text or sentences into other languages.

Applications : Augmented Reality: Identifying and viewing the real world in other applications. Cryptography: Applications of artificial intelligence for security. : Areas such as marketing, commercial analysis, customer service.

Security and Privacy : Security analysis: Support of artificial intelligence algorithms to detect malicious activity. Privacy: Application of artificial intelligence to protect personal data.

ChatGPT , on the other hand, is a type of artificial intelligence and is used by educators, marketing service providers, and other organizations. ChatGPT is a text assistant and can answer several questions asked by users. ChatGPT is also used to perform actions such as asking users other questions and answers, viewing documents, ordering various services, searching for information, etc. These chatbots and virtual assistants have their own capabilities and services. Siri , Alexa, and Google Assistant are voice-enabled services. ChatGPT is also a text-based service. Together, they play an important role in providing user-friendly and efficient services. The advantages include improving user experience and customer support, improving accessibility for people with disabilities, and saving time by automating repetitive tasks. in the presence of the possibility. Disadvantages include complex or ambiguous query comprehension, privacy concerns associated with limited data collection and use. b) Machine translation (Machine Translation). The purpose of machine translation is to overcome language barriers and ensure seamless communication between speakers of different languages. Examples include Google Translate, DeepL, and Microsoft Translator. Google Translate is a service that provides translation of text from one language to another using artificial intelligence and translation technologies. This service helps to read and translate text, speech and even images in several languages. Google Translate works with a large database, artificial intelligence and translation models. These models help in language analysis, individual analysis of words, sentences and sentences, words and their translation, translation and preparation. Google Translate has several language-learning translation models that are well-designed to determine the best translation results by testing and evaluating them extensively. In doing so, Google handles the translated texts with additional analysis and prediction algorithms, and also uses text analysis to better analyze the data. Google Translate performs very well in translating into several languages around the world and is considered a user-friendly and efficient service. Both DeepL and Microsoft Translator are translation services and use

artificial intelligence (AI) and translation technologies. DeepL uses several SI models and systems to provide high-quality translation results when translating from one language to another. These models help in the analysis of the original text, the explanation of the text, translation and correction, the analysis of the translated text and the development of translation models. It works with language analysis and translation models to deliver high-quality translation results. Microsoft Translator also uses additional analysis algorithms of its language (such as key variables, morphological analysis, language copy analysis) to analyze texts.

Microsoft has also developed a Human Parity evaluation model to compare analysis and translation results with other services. In general, DeepL and Microsoft Translator are effective services in providing high-quality translation results. Also, the features used to analyze each language and develop translation models are different when compared to each other. The advantages of machine translation are that it facilitates global communication and collaboration, reduces the need for human translators, and enables continuous improvement through SI advances. Disadvantages may include incorrect translations for phrases or complex sentences, and errors with context-specific translations.

Computer Vision. Computer vision enables machines to understand and interpret visual information in the world. Some popular computer vision services include: a) Facial recognition. Computer Vision, or CV, is a type of artificial intelligence that enables computers to learn and understand what they see, objects, and images. Face recognition is one of the main functions of CV and provides the ability to automatically validate faces and images. Facial recognition systems work by using sophisticated algorithms and data analysis to identify any object or human face in images or videos. These systems perform steps such as capturing images, extracting data, identifying an object or person, and analyzing the data to understand the image. Facial recognition systems have different principles of operation, some are designed to learn the system, and some are designed to serve other purposes. For example, FaceID is a facial recognition system developed by Apple that is used in the iPhone and iPad Pro. This system uses 30 imaginary points and algorithms based on the imagined demand to detect the user's face. Other systems are facial recognition systems that are designed for other purposes and can be used in various industries such as travel, commerce, sales, medicine, etc. Facial recognition systems are developed by studying the features and applications of human faces and images. In this help, images or videos are studied and the learned information is used to build new systems. Facial recognition systems are used in human, commercial, medical and many other fields. For example: We can get Clearview AI, Amazon Rekognition and Microsoft Azure

Face APIs. Clearview AI is an image facial recognition system for security services. This system enables facial recognition for security agencies by storing and using images of millions of people. Amazon Rekognition is a system developed by Amazon and used in various industries such as commerce, medicine and security. This system provides features such as face detection, face recognition and face verification. Microsoft Azure Face API is a system developed by Microsoft and is used for face recognition, face recognition and face verification. This system is used in commercial, security, and various industries. They perform steps such as capturing images, extracting data, identifying an object or person, and analyzing the data to understand the image. Such systems are commonly used for a variety of purposes such as product procurement, personal identification, and security for a wide range of services. Advantages of these systems include enhanced security and tracking capabilities, simplified authentication processes, and personalized marketing and advertising.

Disadvantages include privacy issues and potential misuse, flaws in facial recognition algorithms, and legal and ethical issues. b) Image and video analysis. The goal of these systems is to automatically detect, classify, and analyze objects in images and videos for a variety of applications, including autonomous vehicles, healthcare, and manufacturing. This system image and video analysis services work on the basis of using deep learning algorithms to extract meaningful information from visual data. Image and video analysis are important areas of computer vision and can be useful for different purposes for users. In this direction, there are various analysis systems such as Google Cloud Vision API, IBM Watson Visual Recognition and OpenCV. Google Cloud Vision API is a closed platform that supports image analysis and text recognition. This system provides capabilities such as image analysis and recognition of objects in the image, text recognition in the image, image search and understanding of the content of the image. IBM Watson Visual Recognition is a system developed by IBM and used for image analysis. This system provides capabilities for image acquisition and comparison, face detection, object detection, image color detection, and services in various fields. OpenCV is a contribution to image and video analysis and is an open source code. This system provides opportunities for image acquisition, object detection, image quality display and various algorithmic operations.

These systems are used for analysis and explanation in various fields. For example, it is used to identify objects with different external characteristics and to confirm text in images. Such systems are also important in various fields such as security, medicine, automotive industry and commerce. They help to ensure

security in the analysis of images and videos by users, and it is also important to know the rights and good guidelines for the use of these systems. 'facilitates data-driven decision-making, improves creative processes through SI-generated content. Disadvantages include high computing power requirements and potential inaccuracies in algorithmic results. Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare. Artificial intelligence has made significant strides in healthcare, with applications ranging from diagnostics to drug discovery. Some of the prominent healthcare SI services include:a) Medical imaging and diagnostics. Examples include Aidoc, Zebra Medical Vision, and PathAI. The purpose of these is to increase diagnostic accuracy, speed up the process, and reduce human error. In these systems, SI algorithms analyze medical images such as X-rays or MRIs to identify patterns and abnormalities that may indicate diseases or medical conditions. The benefits of this service include improved diagnostic accuracy and early detection, reduced workload for health care providers, and personalized treatment plans.

Disadvantages include dependence on the quality of study data, algorithmic biases and ethical concerns, and potential overreliance on SI. This leads to a decrease in the human experience.b) Discovery and development of drugs. Examples include DeepMind's AlphaFold, Atomwise, and Insilico Medicines. The goal is to speed up the drug discovery process, reduce costs, and increase the success rate of new drugs. These SI algorithms analyze large data sets to identify potential drug candidates, predict their efficacy, and optimize their chemical structures. The benefits of this technology include a faster and more efficient drug discovery process, cost reductions for pharmaceutical companies and patients, and treatment of rare or complex diseases. consists of opportunities to discover new methods. Disadvantages include limited understanding of complex biological systems, intellectual property and data sharing issues, and regulatory challenges in SI-guided drug development.

Summary

Artificial intelligence has infiltrated many aspects of our lives, offering innovative solutions and changing industries. As artificial intelligence technology continues to develop, it is important to strike a balance between reaping its benefits and addressing the relevant ethical, legal, and social implications. Thus, artificial intelligence is of great importance today, and its consumption field is expanding day by day. When artificial intelligence (AI) is created, it can also have several potential harms. In addition, it may lead to regulatory issues such as advanced monitoring, ethical issues, safety and welfare issues to prevent harm. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has great benefits in several fields and is being applied to various industries. With this widespread use and development of artificial

intelligence, there is scope for even more uses for various industries in the future. If it is used for the right purpose, I think it will give us unprecedented success. With its help, humanity has been using it to alleviate its problems. As mentioned above, it has penetrated into many fields. But it does not always give good results, it is necessary to take into account the benefits as well as the harms. It is in the hands of mankind to turn it into a powerful force and a dangerous weapon. Therefore, it is advisable to use it wisely!

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